

INTERPERSONAL RELATIONS IN THE BRIDAL SEAMSTRESS STORY (THE DEW BREAKER) BY EDWIDGE DANTICAT

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Abstract. This article provides an in-depth analysis of how interpersonal relations are skillfully described and their functions in the short story “The Bridal Seamstress” from the book *The Dew Breaker* by Haitian-American author Edwidge Danticat. It examines how Danticat employs subtle details, actions, dialogues, backgrounds and inner life of the main character main character, Beatrice Saint Fort, an aging Haitian-American immigrant bridal seamstress to depict her emotional connection with her clients. The article explores how this short story provides commentary on well-rounded depiction of social bonding and the influence of interpersonal relations on the main character’s life.

Keywords: interpersonal relations, physical trauma, emotional despondency, painful memories, shared understanding.

Introduction An acclaimed author, Edwidge Danticat’s short story collection consists of nine closely correlated stories. Different characters participate in each story, however, the title character, a former torturer under the Duvalier dictatorship in Haiti plays a primary role and all stories revolve around it. The sixth story “The Bridal Seamstress” mainly deals with traumas of retiring seamstress, who makes a living by making wedding dresses and torments caused by torturer’s particular cruelty. In her short story collection *The Dew Breaker*, Edwidge Danticat describes interpersonal relations between characters very skillfully. All events revolve around the main character, Beatrice whose life is dominated by the severe torture that she experienced in Haiti. Throughout the narrative, various interpersonal relationships are explored, illuminating the themes of sacrifice, trauma and the impact it has on individuals and their connections with others. While the story doesn’t delve into Beatrice’s interpersonal relations with her clients vividly, it does provide glimpses of her interactions with them.

Beatrice remains haunted into old age by brutal treatment experienced decades prior by a member of the Duvalier regime’s notorious tonton macoutes paramilitary. Despite having suffered torments from prison inmate, she is

described as a tolerant and dedicated person who believes in her willpower to make her gloomy past days into bright and prosperous ones. The relationship between Beatrice and her clients are depicted as one of trust and collaboration. She handles dresses not just as pieces of fabric but as pieces of love and celebration. She comprehends that the emotional significance, years of tortures, unbearable painful memories and trauma are attached to these garments.

Literature review Previous researches have not studied the story “Bridal Seamstress” from the point of the significance and influence of interpersonal relations. Eman Mostafa Ahmed Atta, assistant professor of Egyptian Institute focused on the way how scars of trauma are described in the story. He emphasized that the scars Beatrice has on her feet can display a metaphor for a mind distorted by fear and pain. This study shows the readers to be aware that Beatrice not only got physical trauma from her torturer, but also mental as well as emotional despondency she has experienced.

Edwidge Danticat’s practice of using euphemisms in “The Dew Breaker” novel was studied by Rebecca Fuchs, a researcher of the Mannheim university. She particularly focused on how beautifully Danticat described the tension between poetic beauty and violence. According to the researcher, euphemistic language is a way of expressing the ambiguous and contradictory quality of trauma and violence.

Discussion Danticat attempts to paint a portrait of a slowly-paced, formal Beatrice devoted to tradition her mutual connection with her clients. Despite Aline’s eagerness to commence the interview, Beatrice insists on leisurely preparing and sharing coffee slowly made from scratch, calling it “one of her secrets” and saying, “I always take time, whether it’s getting dressed, making coffee, or sewing wedding gowns”[1;124]. From this description it is clear that Beatrice has a great patience in doing anything whether it is making a coffee or sewing dresses. She is a good listener and sympathetic. She approaches everything meticulously showing professionalism and expertise. She conducts fittings, listens to their clients’ preferences and makes the necessary adjustments to ensure that the dress fits them perfectly. In this way, she conquers the heart and attains admiration of her clients. The relationship between Beatrice and her clients is built on trust and a shared understanding. Moreover, Danticat prefers to use some motifs in the story in order to give a vivid explanation to the personality of Beatrice and how she is closely connected with her profession. For instance, the dresses that Beatrice makes play an essential role in her life as they function as an embodiment of her soul, heart and

individuality. Her soul is as white as a wedding dress. However, this soul has experienced intolerable torments and sufferings during the course of her life. Beatrice considers herself like a wedding dress. When her clients wears a dress, she imagines that all people are looking at her. “ And the way I see it, I am that dress. It is like everyone is looking at me”[1;127].The thing that can only heal this soul is getting positive comments from clients and this provides her a temporary release from the horrible experiences in the past. Working as a bridal seamstress is one of the elements that can allow the reader to identify Beatrice’s character and true personality. This profession helps her to maintain strong and affectionate relationships with her clients. Therefore, in the interview she says that she calls her clients “my girls” and her clients call her “mother” [1;126]. Although Beatrice has never been married so far, she has children and her children are her clients. In short, through her work as a bridal seamstress, Beatrice is able to achieve the most glorious and respectable name “mother”, which substitutes for the tortures she experienced in the past. Beatrice does not believe anyone or anything except for her clients as past damage has a profound impact on her current life. Aline notes of Beatrice in the story “ In spite of her size she has a loud commanding voice, like someone who was accustomed to giving orders” [1;122]. In the story Beatrice is depicted as a tiny woman, however, this feature cannot make her a passive character rather an assertive and self-dependent strong individual. Beatrice tells to Alice “ In all that time, I’ve sewn every stitch myself. Never had anyone helping me. Never could stand anyone in my house for too long” [1;126]. This characterization can reveal how mature and tolerant she is. She has a strong perseverance, determination and tolerance that encourage readers to adopt these traits and never give up no matter what happens in life.

Conclusion In “The Bridal Seamstress” short story within The Dew Breaker collection, acclaimed Haitian-American writer Edwidge Danticat masterfully describes interpersonal relations between Beatrice and her clients as well as the influence of this mutual bonding into her current life. Beatrice uses her interpersonal connection with her clients to provide them with emotional support and healing. Many of her clients have experienced trauma or difficult circumstances, and through their conversations, Beatrice is able to provide empathy and understanding. This aspect of their relationship highlights the power of human connection in helping individuals heal and move forward. Moreover, through maintaining strong bonds with her clients, Beatrice creates her new identity and new self.

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